

ENHANCEMENT OF INTERFACIAL ADHESION IN GLASS FIBER/EPOXY COMPOSITES USING GRAPHENE NANOSHEETS

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ABSTRACT

Glass fiber/graphene multiscale composites were obtained by direct electrophoretic deposition (EPD) of graphene oxide nanosheets (GO) onto glass fibers (GF). Modified Hummer's method and subsequent ultrasonication technique was used to create GO suspension from graphite source. The GO suspension, being a stable aqueous dispersion of graphene oxide in water, was used as a bath for EPD process. The GO, being negatively charged due to liquid oxidation technique, was deposited on glass fibers by placing them in front of an anode. Different voltages were applied up to 10 V/cm under direct current (DC). As reported in Figure 1, electron microscopy characterization of the coated glass fibers revealed a quite uniform coating of GO nanosheets that resulted to completely wrap the glass fibers. The amount of GO deposited on the GF resulted to steadily increase as the voltage applied during the EPD process increased. These hierarchical fibers were aligned within a bicomponent epoxy polymer matrix to create hybrid single-fiber microcomposites. The interfacial adhesion in glass fiber/epoxy composites was evaluated by the single-fiber fragmentation tests. An increase of the interfacial shear strength (ISS) was observed for GO coated glass fibers compared with as-received ones. The increase of ISS values resulted to be proportional to the amount of GO deposited on the GF up to an improvement of a factor 2.18. The observed increase in interlaminar shear strength could be attributed to an improvement of interphase thermo-mechanical properties due to GO coating. Moreover, the nanomodified interphase could provide a better mechanical interlocking between GF and matrix, due to increased surface roughness.

1 INTRODUCTION

In modern engineering applications, the use of fiber reinforced polymer composites (FRPC) has increased to a great extent as compared to metals. Noticeable example is the use FRPC in aviation industry e.g Airbus A350, Boeing 787 etc. The basic requirements of such composites materials include superior specific strength, fatigue resistance and simultaneous existence of other functional properties like electrical and thermal conductivity, self-healing etc.

An effective interface is a prime requirement for the mechanical performance of such high strength composites. A transfer of stresses takes place through the fiber-matrix interface via a combination of mechanical interlocking, chemical bonding and physical adhesion [1]. However, the absence of reactive functional groups on the fiber surface and poor wettability hinders the effective transfer of load between fibers and matrix. Hence the key focus in the research areas of both academia and industries is to enhance the interfacial properties between fiber and matrix.

Various strategies can be employed to improve the adhesion strength between fibers and matrices. A recent review paper by Karger-Kocsis et al. [2] described the most common methods which are classified on the basis of the selected strategies distinguishing between i) interphase tailoring via sizing/coating on fibers, ii) creation of hierarchical fibers by nanostructures, iii) fiber surface modifications by polymer deposition and iv) potential effects of matrix modifications on the interphase formation. Especially there has been a great interest in developing hierarchical micro/nano composites in recent years, specifically on the integration of nanoscale reinforcement on fibers [3, 4]. In past,

growth or deposition of carbon nanotubes on reinforcements for better interfacial adhesion has been reported in numerous articles. Techniques like chemical vapor deposition (CVD) [5], grafting [6, 7], electrophoretic deposition (EPD) [8] has been successfully employed for the growth/deposition of nanomaterials on various fibers. Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) have been used as an interphase between fiber and matrix resulting in improved bonding, IFSS, flexural modulus as well as electrical conductivity [9-11].

Graphene having high electron mobility, exceptional thermal conductivity and outstanding mechanical properties has been considered to be a promising and exciting research area [12-14]. The incorporation of graphene in polymer based composites has resulted in improved performance due to the interfacial interactions (either hydrophobic-hydrophobic interactions, weak van der Waal's forces and π - π stacking) between polymers and graphene-based materials [15-19]. Graphene oxide (GO) with oxygen-containing polar functionalities like carboxy, carbonyl, epoxide and hydroxyl groups gives possibility of interactions with polymer matrix [20]. The modulus of the polymer composites increases greatly due to the interfacial crosslinking [21] whereas electrostatic interactions are also important which result in the nanocomposites to be much stronger and tougher [22].

In this paper, GO is used as an interphase in glass fiber/epoxy composites and interfacial properties are reported. GO is deposited on glass fibers by EPD and subsequent composite is tested for interfacial shear strength.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Materials and Methods

All chemical purchased were of analytical grade and used without further purification. Graphene oxide was synthesized using an approach similar to Hummer's method [23]. The obtained suspension was washed thoroughly using HCl solution and distilled water to remove Mn ions and acid respectively. The brown solution was dried in a vacuum oven at 50°C for at least 36 hours.

E-glass fibers (Manufacturer: PPG, trade name: 2001) having a diameter of $25.1 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$ were coated by graphene oxide using electrophoretic deposition as shown in the following schematic diagram.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of electrophoretic deposition (EPD) of graphene oxide (GO) onto glass fibers.

Uniform deposition of graphene nanosheets is possible using a stable suspension of GO. To prepare the suspension, a measured amount of graphite oxide powder was sonicated in distilled water for 1 hour. Since glass fiber is insulating in nature, hence two copper plates were used as electrodes while the glass fibers (fixed on a window frame) were placed in front of the anode. This is because graphene oxide will travel towards anode due to the negative charged functional groups attached to graphene sheets through the oxidation process. The deposition was carried out at different applied field (V/cm) using various voltages. To obtain a homogenous deposition around the fiber, a second EPD cycle was performed while reversing the glass fibers. The coated samples were dried in a vacuum oven at 40 °C for 12 hours.

To compare the effect of oxygen functionalities on graphene nanosheets, a set of glass fibers coated with reduced graphene oxide (rGO) were also used for microcomposite preparation. Reduction of graphene oxide on glass fiber was carried out by subjecting the coated fibers to an environment of hydrazine hydrate vapors followed by drying in an oven at 100 °C for 24 hours.

3 CHARACTERIZATION AND RESULTS

X-ray diffraction technique was used to find out the level of oxidation on graphite using Rigaku III D-max diffractometer (monochromatic radiation Cu-K α line with $\lambda = 51.54056\text{\AA}$). Measurements were carried out in the range of 5-80° 2 θ with a step size of 0.04°. The diffractogram of graphite in figure 2 shows a diffraction peak located at 2 $\theta = 26.5^\circ$ indicating a highly organized crystallized structure. Due to oxidation, graphite oxide diffractogram peak shifts to 10.9° with relatively less intensity thus confirming the oxidation of graphite. The association of oxygen functional groups with graphene layers due to oxidation shifts the diffraction peak [24]. After reduction, rGO displays a diffraction peak at 24.9° due to removal of oxygen functional groups from the sheets of graphene oxide.

Figure 2: XRD comparison plot of graphite, GO and rGO

A Nicolet Avatar 330 device with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} resolution was used to obtain a Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of graphite powder, graphene oxide powder and reduced graphene oxide powder. The samples were individually mixed with potassium bromide (KBr) powder to form homogeneous mixtures and thin discs for analysis were made in a compression mold at 10 bar pressure. The FTIR spectra of graphite, GO and rGO are reported in Figure 3. GO has an increased amount of epoxy C-O groups at 1085 cm^{-1} , C=O groups at 1625 cm^{-1} and O-H group at 3830 cm^{-1} confirm the increased level of oxidation of graphite hence producing the graphite oxide. Moreover, due to the exposure to hydrazine hydrate, these groups were reduced in rGO sample to a level comparable to that of pristine graphite.

Figure 3: FT-IR comparison plot of graphite, GO and rGO

The coatings of GO on glass fiber were investigated by using a field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM) by Zeiss SUPRA 40 microscope. Approximately 5 nm thick layer of platinum was deposited on samples prior to FESEM observations. The fig 4 shows an overview of the quality of graphene oxide coating on the glass fibers. With increasing the applied field from 2.5V/cm to 10V/cm , the glass fibers show a more uniform deposition of graphene oxide. With magnification on individual fibers, it can also be observed that the fibers have more layers of graphene oxide deposited.

Figure 4: SEM images of glass fibers coated with GO – comparison of deposition amount of GO with applied field of a) 2.5 V/cm, b) 5 V/cm, c) 7.5 V/cm, d) 10 V/cm.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis was done by using a Mettler DSC 30 calorimeter. Analysis was performed at a heating rate of 10 °C/min and a constant nitrogen flux of 100 mL/min was maintained during the test in the temperature range from 0 to 80°C. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed using a Mettler TG 50 thermobalance at a heating rate of 10°C/min and 100 mL/min of nitrogen flux during the test with a temperature range of 25-750°C. Mechanical properties of the epoxy polymer were determined using an Instron® 5969 universal testing machine. At least five ISO 527 type 1BA specimens of polymer matrix were prepared and the tests were carried out at a crosshead speed of 10 mm·min⁻¹ with 1% axial deformation. The elastic modulus was measured as a secant value between deformation levels of 0.05 and 0.25% as per ISO 527 standard.

The physical properties of epoxy resin are summarized in Table 1.

Physical Property		Value
Glass transition temperature (T _g)	[°C]	28
Thermal degradation	[°C]	340
Yield stress	[MPa]	22.3
Tensile Modulus	[MPa]	26.1
Young's Modulus	[MPa]	798.2

Table 1: Physical properties of epoxy resin

Single-fiber fragmentation tests (SFFT) were carried out by a tensile tester (Minimat, by Polymer Laboratories, Loughborough, UK). A polarized optical stereo-microscope (Wild M3Z by Leica) was used to observe the fiber fragmentation process during the tensile test. Minimum strain of 10% was applied to each specimen at a cross-head speed of 10 mm/min in order to assure the saturation of the fragmentation process. An image analysis software (ImageJ) was used to measure the mean fiber length at saturation (L_s). The value of critical fiber length, L_c was considered to be equal to 0.75 L_s . The simplified micromechanical models proposed by Kelly and Tyson [25] were used to calculate interfacial shear strength (ISS) values. Equilibrium between the tensile force acting on a fiber and the shear force transferred through the fiber–matrix interface results in an average value of ISS according to the following equation:

$$ISS = \frac{\sigma_{fb}(L_c)d}{2L_c} \quad (1)$$

where d is the fiber diameter and $\sigma_{fb}(L_c)$ is the tensile strength of a fiber at the critical length.

This latter value can be estimated by assuming a Weibull distribution for the fiber strength, i.e.:

$$\sigma_{fb}(L_c) = \sigma_0 \left(\frac{L_c}{L_0} \right)^{-\frac{1}{m}} \Gamma \left(1 + \frac{1}{m} \right) \quad (2)$$

where Γ is the Gamma function, whereas σ_0 and m are the scale and shape parameters of the Weibull strength distribution at the reference length L_0 , respectively.

The scale and shape parameters were estimated from strength data of single fiber. In particular, single filaments of fiber were tested using the ASTM standard C1557-03. Specimens with gage length of 20 mm were tested with an Instron 4502 universal tensile tester equipped with a 10 N load cell tested at a cross head speed of 0.2 mm/min. An iterative procedure originally proposed by Gurvich et al. [26] was used for the data reduction, data which is summarized in Table 2.

Parameter		Value
n (number of tests)	-	31
σ_0	[MPa]	1476.1
m (shape parameter)	-	4.4
\bar{R} (average strength)	[MPa]	1007
Δ	-	-0.37
ν	[%]	28.2

Table 2: Mechanical properties of glass fibre as determined from single fibre tensile tests.

ISS values based on the saturation length of the fiber fragments measured in SFFT are listed in table 3. It is clear from the calculated values that the fragment lengths decreased with the increase of the field of electrophoretic deposition. This is basically due to an increase in ISS between fiber and matrix.

State of Deposition (Field V/cm)	Average Fragment Length (mm)	Critical Length (mm)	Tensile strength of fiber ($\sigma_{fb(L_c)}$) MPa	ISS (MPa)
As Received	2.65	3.53	1474.8	5.72
2.5	2.0	2.7	1546.5	7.00
5	1.72	2.30	1611.2	8.89
7.5	1.21	1.61	1742.2	14.62
10	0.94	1.26	1843.8	18.22

Table 3: ISS values in according to Kelly–Tyson model as determined by average fragment length and tensile strength of fiber

The increase of ISS by a factor of 2.18 is basically due to favorable bonding between the glass fibers and epoxy resin due to graphene oxide hence enhancing the effective distribution of load on the fibers. additionally mechanical interlocking between GF and matrix due to increased surface roughness and the covalent bonding between GFs and GO could also be responsible for the increased ISS in composites [27]. Hence the graphene oxide interphase sufficiently enhances the interfacial adhesion between reinforcement and polymer matrix.

To confirm this, reduced GO was used between epoxy and GF in order to compare the effect of functional groups on adhesion between glass fiber reinforcement and polymer matrix. Reduction of deposited GO on GF was carried out by exposing it to hydrazine hydrate vapors. The reduction was

confirmed by XRD and FTIR analysis (see figures 2 and 3). As per practice, single fiber composites were then made and tested by fragmentation test. The plot in figure 6 compares the ISS between single fiber composites coated by GO and rGO.

Figure 5: Comparison of effect of GO and rGO on ISS of glass fiber/epoxy composite

After a slight increase of ISS in case of rGO as shown in figure 5, the value remains constant throughout the applied field. These values are systematically lower than the one observed in microcomposites containing GO coated fibers. This positively backs our hypothesis that favorable bondings due to functional groups play a major role in enhanced ISS. Additionally, the absence of oxygen functionalities on the rGO sheets practically limits the possibility of chemical bonding between rGO and epoxy matrix. Moreover, the substantial independency of ISS values from the applied deposition voltage confirms that the main load-transfer mechanism is only based on the mechanical interlocking in this case.

4 CONCLUSIONS

GO synthesized through modified Hummer's method was deposited on E-glass fiber by electrophoretic deposition under the application of different voltages. Interfacial shear strength between matrix and fiber was evaluated by the fragmentation test on epoxy based microcomposites. This resulted in proportional increase of ISS to the applied field and a maximum improvement of 218% was observed. This increase of interlaminar shear strength due to GO coating is a combined effect of i) favorable chemical bonding between GF and GO and ii) mechanical interlocking between GF and matrix. Conversely, chemically reduced graphene oxide coatings resulted to be less effective in improving the ISS values, with a maximum increment of 40%.

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